

Structure-function relation of cytokinins determines their differential efficiency in mediating tobacco resistance against *Pseudomonas syringae*

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1 **Abstract**

2 The classic plant growth-promoting phytohormone cytokinin has been identified and established also as
3 a mediator of pathogen resistance in different plant species. However, the resistance effect of structurally
4 different cytokinins appears to vary and may regulate diverse mechanisms to establish resistance. Hence,
5 we comparatively analysed the impact of six different adenine- and phenylurea-type cytokinins on the
6 well-established pathosystem *Nicotiana tabacum-Pseudomonas syringae*. The efficiency of resistance
7 effects was evaluated based on impacts on the host plant defence response by scoring infection
8 symptoms and the direct impact on the pathogen by assessment of proliferation *in planta*. To identify
9 common and cytokinin-specific components involved in resistance effects, transcriptome profiling and
10 targeted metabolomics were conducted in leaves treated with the different cytokinins. We observed
11 clearly different potentials of the tested cytokinins in either suppressing infection symptoms or pathogen
12 proliferation. Gene regulation and metabolite analyses revealed cytokinin-type specific impacts on
13 defence components, such as salicylic acid and related signalling, expression of PR proteins, and
14 regulation of specialised metabolism. Cytokinins also strongly affected plant cell physiological
15 parameters, such as a remarkable decrease in amino acid pools. Hence, this study provides comparative
16 information on the efficiency of diverse cytokinins in mediating resistance in one well-studied
17 pathosystem and insights in the specific regulation of resistance effects mediated by different cytokinin
18 molecules. This is particularly relevant for studies on the function of cytokinins or other phytohormones
19 and compounds interacting with cytokinin activities in the context of pathogen infections and other stress
20 scenarios, considering the diverse cytokinins present in plants.

21 **1 Introduction**

22 Phytohormones comprise different groups of important signalling molecules that play significant roles
23 in regulating virtually all plant processes and interactions with their environment. Established
24 phytohormones are namely abscisic acid (ABA), auxins, brassinosteroids, cytokinins (CKs), ethylene,
25 jasmonic acid (JA), salicylic acid (SA) and strigolactones, while other molecules are being discussed as
26 additional potential phytohormones. Classically, these phytohormones have been divided into growth-
27 regulating and stress signalling compounds. Recently, increasing information accumulates that the major
28 functions attributed to specific phytohormones within growth regulation OR stress signalling is often
29 complemented with relevant functions in the other processes (Pieterse et al., 2012; Shigenaga et al.,
30 2017; Großkinsky & Petrášek, 2019). Hence, phytohormones in general, but also individual
31 phytohormone groups can be regarded as pivotal physiological hubs regulating and balancing between
32 growth- and stress-related processes.

33 CKs form one essential group of classic growth-regulating and -promoting phytohormones. CKs have
34 been named after their central function in driving the cell cycle and have been also intensely studied for
35 their physiological functions (Roitsch & Ehneß, 2000; Sakakibara, 2006; Argueso & Kieber, 2024).
36 Their structure is based on adenine with modification of the side chain at the N⁶ position (Sakakibara,
37 2006). Major naturally occurring CKs are the *cis*- and *trans*-isomers of zeatin (cZ, tZ), dihydrozeatin
38 (DHZ), 2-isopentenyl adenine (2-iP), their conjugates and derivatives, while other adenine-based CKs,
39 such as 6-benzylaminopurine (6-BAP) and kinetin (Kin), are commonly used alternatives. Furthermore,
40 phenylurea-based compounds, such as thidiazuron (TDZ) or chloro-pyridyl-phenylurea, are used as
41 growth regulators with CK activities. Together with auxin, CK is the essential phytohormone
42 determining proliferation and differentiation in plant cells and tissues (Schaller et al., 2015; Großkinsky
43 & Petrášek, 2019). Hence, CKs are central to proper plant growth and development. Their link to central
44 carbohydrate metabolism by regulating essential enzyme activities indicates an important role in
45 balancing energy distribution/allocation (Ehneß & Roitsch, 1997; McIntyre et al., 2021). The intimate
46 interaction with carbohydrate metabolism is also essential for the classic CK effect of delaying
47 senescence (Mothes, 1960; Lara et al., 2004; Behr et al., 2012), stabilising plant cells and tissues. In
48 contrast, imbalances in CK homeostasis cause dysfunctional organogenesis and abnormal growth
49 phenotypes. These CK functions and effects underpin their roles in directly impacting and determining
50 the physiological status of plant at organismic and tissue levels.

51 In recent years, CKs have been studied for their roles in plant interactions with their environment and
52 particularly functions in regulating immunity and defence mechanisms against pathogens were
53 identified (Akhtar et al., 2019). By different approaches ranging from exogenous application of CKs
54 and genetic modulation of CK biosynthesis or signalling, to the treatment with CK-producing beneficial
55 microbes, increases in CK levels were shown to have the potential to improve plant resistance to
56 different pathogens. By exogenous application of CKs, this effect was shown to be dose dependent
57 (Babosha, 2009; Großkinsky et al., 2011; Argueso et al., 2012). The biocontrol ability of CK-producing

58 bacteria (Großkinsky et al., 2016) and microalgae (Sandor et al., 2024) demonstrates an interkingdom
59 signalling function of CK produced by plant beneficial microbes. Studied plant species include
60 *Arabidopsis thaliana*, *Oryza sativa*, *Triticum aestivum* and *Nicotiana tabacum*, in which the resistance
61 towards mainly (hemi-)biotrophic pathogens such as *Hyaloperonospora arabidopsidis*, *Erysiphe*
62 *graminis*, *Magnaporthe oryzae* or *Pseudomonas syringae*, was increased by CKs (Barna et al., 2008;
63 Babosha, 2009; Choi et al., 2010; Großkinsky et al., 2011, 2013, 2014, 2016; Argueso et al., 2012; Jiang
64 et al., 2013; Sandor et al., 2024). While some pathogens seem to hijack CK accumulation and signalling
65 when establishing their infection niches (Behr et al., 2012; Hann et al., 2014), the identified resistance
66 effects appear to be a wide-spread phenomenon in diverse pathosystems. Depending on the pathosystem
67 studied, CK-mediated effects have been shown to interact with other phytohormones, such as SA and
68 ABA, expression of specific pathogenesis-related (PR)-genes, the activation of the antioxidant system
69 and/or increased accumulation of antimicrobial compounds such as phytoalexins (Barna et al., 2008;
70 Choi et al., 2010; Ko et al., 2010; Großkinsky et al., 2011, 2014; Argueso et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013)
71 and CKs may also directly impact the virulence of pathogens such as *Botrytis cinerea* (Gupta et al.,
72 2021). In addition to activating defence and resistance mechanisms, plant physiological functions of
73 CKs, e.g., regulating carbohydrate/energy allocation (Roitsch & Ehneß, 2000; McIntyre et al., 2021),
74 may further contribute to reduced disease establishment by improving tolerance to pathogen infections.
75 Although several studies have been conducted to identify CK-mediated resistance effects, these only
76 explain a part of the underlying mechanisms. Furthermore, only limited information is available about
77 the potential of different CK molecules to improve resistance or tolerance towards pathogen infections
78 and the CK-specific underlying mechanisms (Großkinsky et al., 2011, 2013; Bozsó & Barna, 2021).
79 Hence, a more detailed and comparative analysis of the activities of individual CKs and components of
80 the underlying mechanisms in relation to disease control is needed. To test our hypothesis that
81 structurally different CKs, comprising naturally occurring and artificial molecules, will have differential
82 impact on plant immunity/resistance, we deployed the well-established system of exogenous CK
83 application to *N. tabacum* leaves by petiole feeding and the infection with *Pseudomonas syringae* pv.
84 *tabaci* (*Pst*), which has been used before to identify CK-mediated resistance effects and components of
85 the underlying mechanisms. To determine possible differences in the effects of six different CKs on this
86 pathosystem, we comparatively scored symptom development (as an estimate of combined defence and
87 tolerance effects) and pathogen proliferation (as an estimate of defence effects) of *Pst* infection after
88 treatments with the adenine-type CKs 2-iP, 6-BAP, cZ, tZ, Kin, and phenylurea-type CK TDZ, as well
89 as respective controls. Furthermore, we conducted targeted metabolome and whole transcriptome
90 profiling to identify factors contributing to common and the expected differential effects of the
91 individual CKs, which may be parts of CK-mediated resistance and tolerance.

92 **2 Materials and Methods**

93 **2.1 Plant materials and growing conditions**

94 Tobacco plants (*Nicotiana tabacum* L. cv. Petit Havana SR1) used in this study were cultivated in
95 commercial substrate (Krukväxtjord Lera & Kisel, SW Horto AB) in a greenhouse at 20 °C to 24 °C
96 with supplementary light from high pressure sodium lamps with an intensity of 100 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and
97 a 16h/8h day/night cycle.

98 **2.2 Cytokinin treatments**

99 Treatments of tobacco leaves from 8- to 10-week-old plants with different cytokinins (CKs) were
100 conducted following a well-established petiole feeding protocol (Großkinsky et al., 2011, 2013, 2014).
101 Briefly, leaves were detached from the plants and petioles were placed into jars filled with 200 mL of
102 10 μM solutions of adenine-derived CKs or adenine as “structural” control, 200 nM thidiazuron (TDZ)
103 or 50 μM NaOH as the solvent control (mock). After 24h, leaves were inoculated with *Pseudomonas*
104 *syringae* (see below) and put on tap water for the remaining experiment. The detached leaves were kept
105 in a light shelf equipped with white light 38W T8 fluorescent tubes (Philipps) with an intensity of 30
106 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$ and a 16h light period at approx. 24 °C.

107 The adenine-derived CKs *cis*-zeatin (cZ; OlChemIm s.r.o.), 2-isopentenyladenine (2-iP), 6-
108 benzylaminopurine (6-BAP), kinetin (Kin), *trans*-zeatin (tZ; all Duchefa Biochemie), the phenylurea-
109 derived CK TDZ (Sigma-Aldrich) and adenine (Sigma-Aldrich) were prepared as stock solutions in 0.5
110 M NaOH. For petiole feeding, the stocks were diluted with tap water to the desired working
111 concentrations. The molecular structures of the used CKs are displayed in Figure S1.

112 For metabolomics and transcriptomics, leaves were sampled after 24h treatment, which constitutes the
113 critical time-point of infection, decisive for the outcome of the infection. To detect early
114 responses/regulations, material treated for 6h was included in transcriptome analyses. For each sample,
115 the midribs of 5 leaves were excised, the leaf blades pooled and snap-frozen in liquid nitrogen. Samples
116 were stored at -80 °C until further use and ground in liquid nitrogen for downstream analyses.

117 **2.3 Pathogen cultivation and infection assays**

118 A tetracycline-resistant strain of *Pseudomonas syringae* pv. *tabaci* (*Pst*) was used for pathogen
119 infections as described before (Großkinsky et al., 2011, 2013, 2014). Briefly, *Pst* was cultivated in liquid
120 LB medium (10 g L⁻¹ NaCl, 10 g L⁻¹ tryptone, 5 g L⁻¹ yeast extract) supplemented with 20 mg L⁻¹
121 tetracycline at 28 °C, shaking at 200 rpm. For each experiment, bacterial cells were pelleted from
122 actively growing cultures by centrifugation. The pellet was resuspended in 10 mM sterile MgCl₂ and
123 adjusted to an OD₆₀₀ of 0.2 (corresponds to approx. 10⁸ cfu mL⁻¹). This suspension was further diluted
124 to the desired infection concentrations of 2·10⁶ cfu mL⁻¹ (symptom development) and 10⁵ cfu mL⁻¹
125 (pathogen proliferation), respectively. Per leaf, six independent intercostal areas were infiltrated with
126 *Pst* suspension from the abaxial surface by a needleless syringe and the inoculated areas were labelled
127 to allow symptom quantification.

128 Symptoms were visually scored at 6 and 12 days post infection (dpi) based on an established scale
129 (Großkinsky et al., 2011), relating symptomatic to inoculated area, with following scores/categories: 0
130 = no symptoms; 0.5 = reduced chlorosis up to 70 %; 1 = more than 70 % chlorosis; 2 = up to 10 %
131 necrosis; 3 = 10 % to 50 % necrosis; 4 = 51 % to 75 % necrosis; 5 = 76 % to 100 % necrosis. For each
132 CK treatment followed by *Pst* infection, in minimum 27 individual leaves were analyzed in a minimum
133 of five independent experiments).

134 Pathogen proliferation was monitored right after infiltration (0h), 24, 48, and 72 h post infection (hpi)
135 according to Yao et al. (2013). Briefly, leaf discs of 4 mm diameter were punched out from infected
136 areas with a cork borer. Each leaf disc was homogenised in 1 mL 10 mM sterile MgCl₂. 10 µL droplets
137 of the suspensions or appropriate dilutions were pipetted in triplicates on solid LB medium
138 supplemented with 20 mg L⁻¹ tetracycline. After the droplets were dried (soaked into the medium), plates
139 were incubated for 24h at 28 °C. Then, microcolonies were counted per droplet using a stereo
140 microscope and cfu mL⁻¹ of the original suspension were calculated considering respective dilutions.
141 *Pst* counts proliferation was determined from a minimum of nine individual leaves analyzed in a
142 minimum of three independent experiments.

143 Results of symptom scores and pathogen proliferation were compared by two-sided, heteroscedastic
144 Student's t-test to identify significant differences between CK treatments and mock control. The effects
145 of CK treatments on both *Pst* proliferation and symptoms were ranked based on average scores.

146 **2.4 RNA extraction, library preparation and sequencing**

147 Total RNA was extracted from sample sets derived from three independent biological experiments. 100
148 mg ground material per sample was extracted using the RNeasy Plant Mini Kit (Qiagen) following the
149 supplier's protocol including on-column DNase digestion (RNase-free DNase set, Qiagen). RNA
150 integrity was checked by TAE gel electrophoresis. RNA purity parameters (OD260/280 & OD260/230)
151 and quantity were determined using the NanoDrop spectrophotometer ND-1000 (Thermo Scientific).
152 Aliquots were prepared and submitted for RNA sequencing (Illumina PE150 HiSeq RNA sequencing),
153 including RNA quality check and library preparation, according to the service provider's requirements
154 (Novogene Bioinformatics Technology Co., Ltd).

155 **2.5 Transcript profiling & gene set enrichment analysis**

156 Raw reads were quality trimmed with BBduk, part of BBTools v38.90 (Joint Genome Institute, 2022),
157 using the suggested parameters for paired-end reads as described in the respective BBduk Guide,
158 including a Kmer length of 23, trimming of reads to the right (ktrim=r), trimming of read regions below
159 an average quality threshold of Q30 (trimq=30), and discarding reads shorter than 50 bp. The mapping
160 was done using the genome published by Edwards et al. (2017), which was sourced through
161 https://solgenomics.net/organism/Nicotiana_tabacum/genome. For both tasks, indexing and mapping,
162 the splice-aware aligner HISAT2 v2.2.1 (Kim et al., 2015) was used with default parameters. For file
163 conversion (sam to bam), samtools v1.14 was used (Li et al., 2009). The mapping was further quality

164 checked using Qualimap v2.2.2a (Okonechnikov et al., 2016) and multiQC v1.11 (Ewels et al., 2016).
165 A read count matrix using the program featureCounts v2.10.5 (Liao et al., 2014) was calculated with
166 default parameters, which was further normalised using variance stabilising transformation (vst) with
167 DESeq2 v1.34.0 (Love et al., 2014). This dataset was first visualised by principal component analysis
168 (PCA) using the R package ggplot2 v3.3.6 (Wickham, 2009). In addition, read counts of selected
169 transcripts were calculated using the functions *estimateSizeFactors* and *counts* of the package DESeq2,
170 which were further scaled to the counts of the Mock treatment, and were plotted using ggplot2. Analysis
171 of differentially expressed genes (DEGs) was done using DESeq2 on the data with the NaOH treatment
172 (=Mock) as the reference level. Results tables were created based on filtering for $\text{padj} < 0.05$ and LFC
173 $> |2|$ (Appendix S1). For the design of the Venn diagrams, the R package venn v1.11 (Dusa, 2022) was
174 used. Through the gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA), a functional profile of a given set of DEGs can
175 be retrieved. For this task, the R packages AnnotationHub v3.2.2 (Morgan & Shepherd, 2022) and
176 clusterProfiler v4.2.2 (Yu et al., 2012) were applied. With the first, a query to the organism database for
177 *Nicotiana tabacum* (AH95991) was done. Using clusterProfiler's function *GSEA*, the gene set
178 enrichment analysis was done, which was plotted using the function *dotplot*. To estimate the global gene
179 expression pattern for the selected GO categories, the shrunken LFC values were computed and
180 visualised as described (Gippert et al., 2022).

181 **2.6 Metabolite extraction and analysis**

182 Three 300 mg fresh weight samples derived from five independent biological experiments were
183 extracted with methanol:chloroform:water as described before (Halbritter et al., 2020). Briefly, samples
184 were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen after sampling and kept at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until extraction. Samples
185 were first homogenised using mortar and pestle with addition of liquid nitrogen and then extracted using
186 methanol:chloroform:water (1:2:2) solution. Aliquot of upper phase was used to analyse amino acids,
187 acids, phenolics and sum of saccharides on LC-MS and individual saccharides on GC-MS. Aliquot of
188 lower phase was taken and used to analyse content of sterols and tocopherol on GC-MS.

189 Samples were analysed for metabolomics twice on HPLC-HRMS with positive and negative polarity of
190 MS-orbitrap to quantify amino acids, acidic and phenolic compounds as well as saccharides (for a
191 detailed list, see Table S1). Both records from DAD detector and from high resolution mass spectrometer
192 were monitored and saved for check of system and evaluation results.

193 For the high-performance liquid chromatography part, a Dionex Ultimate 3000 (Thermo Fisher
194 Scientific, USA/Dionex RSLC, Dionex, USA) was used. The column used was a Hypersil Gold column
195 (C18) 150 mm x 2.1mm, 3 μm (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). Flow rate of mobile phases was 0.3
196 mL min^{-1} and column temperature was set to $30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The HPLC mobile phase consisted of (A)
197 acetonitrile and (B) water containing 0.1 % acetic acid. Both mobile phases (A) and (B) were filtrated
198 and degassed for 10 min in an ultrasonic bath prior to use. Gradient elution chromatography was
199 performed starting with 10 % acetonitrile (A) and 90 % water (0.1 % acetic acid) (B) and held 5 minutes.

200 Within time interval (5-20 minutes), A % composition was increased to 90 %. This composition was
201 then maintained for 5 min. after which the system was 5 min equilibrated to initial conditions (10 %
202 acetonitrile (A) and 90 % water (0.1 % acetic acid). Wavelengths of 254, 272, 274, 331nm were
203 monitored.

204 MS and MSⁿ were performed using a LTQ Orbitrap XL- high resolution mass spectrometer (Thermo
205 Fisher Scientific, USA) equipped with a HESI II (Heated electrospray ionisation) source. The high-
206 resolution mass spectrometer (Orbitrap) was operated in Full Scan with resolution 60 000. Full scan
207 spectra were acquired over mass range m/z 50-1000 in positive mode and 65-1000 in negative mode.
208 The resolution and sensitivity of the Orbitrap were controlled by injection of mixed standard (phenolic
209 compounds) after analysing of each 25 samples and resolution was also checked by the help of lock
210 masses (phthalates). Blanks were also analysed during sequence. The compounds were searched in the
211 mass library which was created from measurement of standards in MS and MSⁿ modes of Orbitrap.

212 Acetonitrile Hypergrade for LC-MS LiChrosolv^R was supplied by Merck KGaA (Darmstadt, Germany).
213 Acetic acid was obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie GmbH (Steinheim, Germany). The Purelab
214 Classic (ELGA LabWater, High Wycombe, Bucks, UK) was used to generate high purity water for
215 preparation of aqueous mobile phase.

216 GC-MS was used to analyse a spectrum of saccharides, sterols, and tocopherol (for a detailed list, see
217 Table S2). For saccharides, samples were prepared for analysis using a two-step derivatisation process:
218 First, a solution of 2.5 % hydroxylamine chloride in pyridine (350 µL) was used and samples were held
219 at 75 °C for 30 min; in the second step, trimethylsilyl (TMS) ethers were obtained by adding a solution
220 of 100 µL of bis(trimethylsilyl)trifluoroacetamide and trimethylchlorosilane (BSTFA+TMCS, 99:1) and
221 heating samples for 60 min at 60 °C. For sterols and tocopherol determination, samples were derivatised
222 using 50 µL of pyridine and 70 µL of BSTFA with 1 % TMS solution and heating samples at 60 °C for
223 30 min. Analyses were performed with a TSQ Quantum XLS triple Quadrupole (Thermo Scientific,
224 USA) on a ZB-5MS capillary column of 30 m (length), 0.25 mm (ID), 0.25 µm (film thickness). For
225 saccharides, the temperature programme was as follows: initial temperature at 100 °C, increase to
226 190 °C at rate 12 °C min⁻¹, held at this temperature for 6 min followed by increase of temperature to
227 250 °C at rate 230 °C min⁻¹, held there for 6 min, and finally programmed to 280 °C at the rate 40 °C
228 min⁻¹ and kept at this temperature for 10 min. The injection temperature was 250 °C, the flow rate of the
229 carrier gas (helium) was 1 mL min⁻¹, and splitless mode was used. The interface temperature was
230 maintained at 250 °C. Mass spectrometry (electron ionisation, 50 eV, ion source temperature 200 °C)
231 was performed at full scan in range 50–450 m/z (scan time 0.17 s). Arabitol was used as an internal
232 standard for determination of saccharides. For sterols and tocopherols, a temperature programme of 1
233 min hold on 220 °C followed by gradual increase at rate 6 °C min⁻¹ to 290 °C (isothermal for 2.5 min)
234 was used. The injection temperature was 280 °C, the carrier gas (helium) flow rate was 1 mL min⁻¹, and
235 the mode was splitless. The temperature of both the mass spectrometry transfer line and the ion source
236 was set at 250 °C. Cholesterol was used as an internal standard.

237 The results derived from 5 independent experiments with 3 technical replicates per sample consisting of
238 5 leaves were used to obtain ratios for each metabolite between the CK treatments and the mock controls
239 based on mean values.

240 **3 Results and Discussion**

241 **3.1 Diverse cytokinins differentially affect *Pst* infection**

242 To test the impact of six structurally different, naturally occurring and artificial adenine- and phenylurea-
243 type CKs on *Pst* infections in *N. tabacum*, detached leaves were pre-treated with CKs for 24h prior to
244 *Pst* infection. The grade of infection was evaluated based on visible symptom development and *Pst*
245 proliferation (Figure 1). While possible restriction in pathogen proliferation indicates activated defence
246 (resistance), potential suppression of symptom development can be a combined result of defence and an
247 improved physiological state of the plant tissue (resistance + tolerance). At both scoring time-points of
248 6 and 12 days post infection (dpi), symptoms were significantly suppressed in CK-treated leaves
249 compared to the mock controls (Figure 1A). While TDZ showed the strongest and 2-iP the weakest
250 suppressive effect on symptom development at both time-points, Kin and cZ appeared to be more
251 effective than 6-BAP and tZ early, but ultimately tZ was more effectively suppressing symptoms at 12
252 dpi than all other adenine-derived CKs. Similarly, differential impact of the different CKs on *Pst*
253 proliferation was observed (Figure 1B). TDZ was most effectively restricting *Pst* proliferation as
254 evidenced by significantly reduced numbers of bacterial cells detected in the plant tissue at all time-
255 points between 24 and 72 h post infection (hpi). The dynamics of the adenine-derived CKs in restricting
256 *Pst* proliferation varied over the time monitored. While 2-iP and tZ caused a significant and Kin a clear
257 restriction of *Pst* proliferation at 24 hpi, no (considerable) effect was seen in leaves treated with 6-BAP
258 and cZ. In contrast, all CK treatments resulted in a significant restriction in *Pst* proliferation at 48 hpi.
259 At 72 hpi, cZ showed no effect anymore, while *Pst* restriction was still clearly detectable for all other
260 CKs.

261 Ranking the effects of the different CKs in suppressing symptom development and restricting *Pst*
262 proliferation shows no clear correlation of these two effects (Table 1). It also further illustrates different
263 dynamics and activities of the compared CKs in these two aspects. While the phenylurea TDZ exhibited
264 the strongest symptom suppression and restriction of *Pst* proliferation, cZ had a good symptom
265 suppressive effect but showed no or only little restriction of *Pst* proliferation. In contrast, 2-iP showed
266 the weakest symptom suppression but a relatively good restriction of *Pst* proliferation (at 24 and 72 hpi).
267 The other CKs showed intermediate effects but clearly differed in the relative strength of their activities.
268 Hence, the tested CKs seem to differentially regulate the components and mechanisms that underly these
269 effects.

270 These results are in agreement with previous findings in various pathosystems that different CKs can
271 have promoting effects on plant disease resistance (e.g., Barna et al., 2008; Babosha, 2009; Choi et al.,
272 2010; Großkinsky et al., 2011; Argueso et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2013). Detailed and comparative

273 information on CK-specific potentials in mediating plant resistance is, however, scarce (Großkinsky et
274 al., 2013; Bozsó & Barna, 2021). Nevertheless, besides the common resistance phenomenon mediated
275 by all CKs tested, the CK-specific variations in this effect are in agreement with their known different
276 potentials to regulate plant (physiological) processes (Polowick & Greyson, 1984; Sul & Korban, 1994;
277 Sujatha & Reddy, 1998; Sakakibara, 2006; Behr et al., 2012; Bozsó & Barna, 2021). These CK-specific
278 variations can be related to their structural differences, which have a potential impact on their transport
279 (uptake into the leaves in the used experimental setup) and which determines their signalling as well as
280 their metabolism (Stolz et al., 2011; Aremu et al., 2013; Hönig et al., 2018). Hence, different dynamics
281 in CK-specific signalling and abundance due to different metabolic routes/rates need to be considered
282 for their structure-specific functions.

283 **3.2 RNA sequencing reveals differential transcriptional regulation by different CKs**

284 To gain insight into the underlying regulatory mechanisms resulting in the differential impact of the
285 tested CKs on *Pst* symptom development and proliferation, transcriptome profiling based on total RNA
286 from leaves have been performed. Leaves pre-treated with the different CKs, adenine as structural
287 control or mock (NaOH) for 6 and 24 h were comparatively analysed. The two time-points allowed for
288 capturing early regulations (6 h) and regulations active at the critical time-point of infection (24 h).

289 The analysis of significantly differentially expressed genes (DEGs; adjusted p-value < 0.05 and LFC >
290 |2|) at 6 and 24h revealed common and CK-specific responses (Figure 2; Appendix S1). Adenine as
291 structural control treatment showed no gene regulation in comparison to the mock control, indicating no
292 activation of plant resistance mechanisms (Figure 2A, C). All CKs except 2-iP revealed similar gene
293 expression dynamics (Figure 2 A, C). At 6h, all CKs resulted in more up-regulated than down-regulated
294 genes, with 2-iP having the highest number of DEGs (Figure 2A). 78 genes were commonly regulated
295 by all CKs; interestingly, also the share of unique DEGs was considerably higher for 2-iP (173) as
296 compared to the other CKs (between 6 and 14 DEGs), indicating an exceptional position of 2-iP (Figure
297 2B). At 24h, the total DEG numbers and the proportion of down-regulated genes increased for all CKs
298 (Figure 2C). Interestingly, at this time-point, 2-iP resulted in the lowest number DEGs (610) compared
299 to the other CKs, which are between 1191 (cZ) and 1716 (Kin) DEGs. 420 genes were commonly
300 regulated by all CKs (Figure 2D); interestingly, all other CKs than 2-iP, shared another 380 commonly
301 regulated genes. This indicates a large overlap of regulations by (most) CKs but again also an
302 exceptional position of 2-iP in gene regulation. While Kin treatment resulted in the highest number of
303 uniquely regulated genes (249), followed by TDZ (182), tZ (125), and 6-BAP (118), cZ uniquely
304 regulated the lowest number (39), but also 2-iP treatment resulted in a relatively low number of uniquely
305 regulated genes (99) compared to the other CKs. The particularly limited regulatory effect of cZ is in
306 agreement with its lower activity often described in comparison to the *trans*-isomer, although specific
307 functions can be attributed to cZ (Schäfer et al., 2015).

308 **3.3 Different CKs activate common and specific pathways and functions**

309 3.3.1 Gene set enrichment analysis

310 Gene set enrichment analysis (GSEA) identified specifically regulated gene classes (Figure 3). At 6h,
311 three gene classes were commonly enriched after different CK treatments (Figure 3A). These included
312 genes involved in “phosphorelay response regulator activity” and in “phosphorelay signal transduction”,
313 representing the regulation of CK signalling components (Argueso & Kieber, 2024), and “regulation of
314 DNA-templated transcription”, indicating a clear impact of CKs on global gene regulation. Treatments
315 with all CKs except cZ also share an enrichment of “catalytic activity”. In addition, after 2-iP treatment,
316 an enrichment in “protein dimerization activity” was observed, and “protein binding” and
317 “oxidoreductase activity” were enriched after 6-BAP, Kin, TDZ and tZ treatment.

318 Regulations of these central cellular functions/components hints at generally high cellular activities
319 driven by CKs, with specificities for each CK. At 24h, a higher number of enriched gene classes than at
320 6h was observed (Figure 3B), indicating early regulations that build up over time, e.g., early regulation
321 of hub genes that affect additional genes via regulatory cascades at 24h. Gene regulations related to
322 “membranes” were only found enriched after 2-iP treatment and genes related to “transmembrane
323 transport” only after 2-iP and 6-BAP treatments. 2-iP and TDZ were lacking enrichment in genes related
324 to “ATP binding” in contrast to the other CKs. Interestingly, 2-iP was the only tested CK which did not
325 result in an enrichment of “chromatin binding regulation”, which may be involved in the CK-mediated
326 regulation of chromatin accessibility (Potter et al., 2018). Hence, this could be a specific feature not
327 efficiently mediated by 2-iP. The GO term “oxidoreductase activity” was found to be enriched after all
328 CK treatments except cZ and Kin, “FAD binding” for 6-BAP, Kin and TDZ, and “O-methyltransferase
329 activity” after 6-BAP and TDZ treatment. These differential but partially overlapping regulations in
330 central cellular functions are indicative of activities contributing to a possibly improved physiological
331 status of the plant tissue which ultimately caused increased pathogen tolerance and resistance.
332 Strikingly, the most efficiently *Pst*-restricting CK TDZ was the only to result in an enrichment of gene
333 regulations associated with response to stress, which underpins its outstanding efficiency in controlling
334 disease establishment. The high efficiency of TDZ is likely to be related to its inhibitory effect on CK
335 oxidases/dehydrogenases, which results in increased levels of endogenous CKs (Nisler, 2018).

336 3.3.2 Regulation of genes belonging to specific GO terms

337 To further dissect gene regulations by the tested CKs, expression changes in genes belonging to selected
338 stress-related GO terms were determined (Figure 4). As CKs restricted *Pst* infection, genes involved in
339 “response to stress” were analysed (Figure 4A), which were regulated at 6 and 24h, with a bigger share
340 of up-regulated expression. The levels of regulation caused by 6-BAP, cZ, Kin, TDZ, and tZ were
341 comparable. In contrast, 2-iP caused the strongest gene regulation at 6h, and the weakest at 24h. The
342 regulation of genes belonging to the GO term “defence response” (Figure 4B) may hint at defence
343 priming effects caused by CKs. Similar to the “response to stress”, regulations were stronger at 24h than
344 at 6h 2-iP resulting in a clearly stronger regulation than the other CKs at the early, and clearly weaker

345 expression at the late time-point. At 6h, the ratio between up- and downregulation is balanced except
346 for 2-iP, while at 24h a considerable shift to stronger upregulation in gene expression was observed for
347 all CK treatments. The regulation of genes belonging to these two GO terms indicated that certain
348 defence mechanisms were triggered by the different CKs, which represents their potential to promote
349 resistance to *Pst* infections by priming these components. In contrast, expressions of genes of the GO
350 term “response to oxidative stress” were mainly down-regulated (Figure 4C), particularly at 6h, while
351 at 24h 2-iP and Kin resulted in stronger up- than downregulation. This strong downregulation may be
352 indicative of an improved tolerance to *Pst* infections by cell and tissue stabilising effects, as the
353 regulation may be a response to generally lowered stress levels and/or associated to an improved stress
354 protective status. Considering observations of the metabolomic analysis (see below), we also checked
355 for gene expression regulations in relation to amino acids. Genes involved in “amino acid biosynthesis”
356 were largely upregulated by all CK treatments at both 6 and 24h (Figure S2A). While only little
357 downregulation was observed at 6h, the share of down-regulated genes increased clearly at 24h.
358 Comparable to the stress-related GO terms, 2-iP resulted again in the strongest regulation of all CKs at
359 6h and the weakest at 24h. In addition to biosynthesis genes, also genes associated to “amino acid
360 catabolism” were clearly regulated (Figure S2B), however, only an upregulation was observed, which
361 was stronger at 24h than at 6h. While at 24h the regulation was comparable between all CK treatments,
362 at 6h, 2-iP and 6-BAP resulted in a lesser upregulation. Notably 2-iP showed a distinct time course with
363 a higher number of regulated genes at 6h compared to 24h. The combined regulation of amino acid
364 biosynthesis and catabolism genes indicates a clear modulation in amino acid pools, and possibly
365 increased turnover rates. This may be an additional indicator of increased cellular activity driven by the
366 applied CKs, in which amino acids may serve as building blocks for proteins, as signalling molecules
367 and as energy source via catabolic processes, contributing to an improved physiological increasing the
368 tolerance to *Pst* and/or priming defence responses (Hildebrandt et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2020;
369 Heinemann & Hildebrandt, 2021). Amino acid transport related genes showed a distinct temporal
370 dynamic (Figure S2C) nonresponse to the CKs. A dominating induction at 6h, with a particular strong
371 impact by tZ, was reversed to a dominating repression at 24h. Although primary metabolic processes
372 were generally repressed by most CKs, except for Kin at 6h and 24h (Figure S2D), specifically
373 carbohydrate metabolism was in contrast increased, in agreement with the established critical role for
374 mediating CK effects (Lara et al., 2004; Roitsch & Gonzalez, 2004) and coordinated induction with
375 direct defence mechanisms (Ehness et al., 1997; Berger et al., 2007). The majority of genes involved in
376 carbohydrate metabolic processes (Figure S2E) and also most genes related to carbohydrate transport
377 (Figure S2F) were induced by all CKs although to different levels in agreement with the finding that the
378 functionally linked extracellular invertase and monosaccharide transporters are coordinately induced
379 by CKs (Ehneß & Roitsch, 1997).

380 ***3.4 Genes associated with pathogen defence mechanisms are differentially regulated by different CKs***

381 3.4.1 Genes of specialised metabolism

382 Next, the regulations of specific genes of interest, which have been studied previously within Kin-
383 mediated resistance to *Pst* in *N. tabacum* (Großkinsky et al., 2011) were visualised for their involvement
384 in defence and resistance mechanisms mediated by any of the tested CKs (Figure 5). The gene encoding
385 the oxidoreductase *3-HYDROXY-3-METHYL-GLUTARYL-CoA REDUCTASE 1 (HMGR1)* is among the
386 unique significantly DEGs up-regulated by Kin (Figure 2). Nevertheless, at a considerably lower level,
387 upregulation was also found at 24h treatments with 6-BAP and TDZ, and at an even lesser extent after
388 2-iP and the zeatin isomers (Figure 5A). *HMGR1* is central to the mevalonate pathway and catalysing
389 the rate-limiting step in the formation of isoprenoids (Vranová et al., 2012). Hence, it regulates the
390 production of diverse important plant metabolites, including pigments, different phytohormones and
391 phytoalexins such as capsidiol, which has been shown to be involved in Kin-mediated resistance
392 (Großkinsky et al., 2011). Considering the weaker upregulation found after treatments with other CKs,
393 it seems to be a particular feature of Kin. Also, expression of the gene encoding *5-EPI-*
394 *ARISTOLOCHENE SYNTHASE (EAS)*, which is involved in capsidiol biosynthesis but not rate-limiting
395 (Keller et al., 1998) was most strongly upregulated by Kin at 6h and 24h treatment, while 2-iP resulted
396 in a strong but transient upregulation at 6h, and low to moderate upregulation was found for the other
397 CKs at 24h (Figure 5B). Hence, the phytoalexin capsidiol may play a particularly important role in Kin-
398 mediated resistance but a comparatively lesser role in the resistance mechanisms of the other CKs.
399 Another phytoalexin important for Kin-mediated resistance is scopoletin, which is derived from the
400 phenylpropanoid pathway. Phenylalanine ammonia-lyase is the first committed step of this pathway and
401 the *PAL1* gene was found to be up-regulated by most of the tested CKs (Figure 5C). Interestingly, 2-iP
402 resulted in a very strong early but transient upregulation, while the zeatin isomers resulted in the
403 strongest upregulation at 24h. Also, Kin resulted in a considerable upregulation at both time-points,
404 confirming previous findings (Großkinsky et al., 2011). Expression of *CINNAMIC ACID 4-*
405 *HYDROXYLASE (C4H)* and *4-COUMARATE:CoA LIGASE 1 (4CLI)*, which are involved in scopoletin
406 biosynthesis, showed different regulation patterns by the CKs (Figure 5D, E). Expression of *C4H* is
407 down-regulated by most CKs (except 2-iP) at 6h and strongly up-regulated by cZ, Kin, tZ and 2-iP at
408 24h (Figure 5D). A specific early upregulation by 2-iP is found for *4CLI*, while all other CKs caused a
409 downregulation at 6h (Figure 5E). At the late time-point, all CKs caused an upregulation of *4CLI*, with
410 the zeatins resulting in the strongest effect, followed by Kin (a similar pattern as for *PAL1*), and a
411 comparable effect of 2-iP, 6-BAP and TDZ. Similarly, the *TOBACCO GLUCOSYL-TRANSFERASE*
412 (*TOGT*) gene, which regulates the conversion between scopoletin and its glucoside scopolin, was only
413 up-regulated by 2-iP at 6h, while otherwise down-regulated by CKs (Figure 5F). At 24h, the strongest
414 upregulation was found after Kin treatment, and to lesser extent by 2-iP and the zeatins; expression after
415 6-BAP and TDZ treatment remained below the mock level also at 24h. The differential regulation of
416 this set of genes indicates a more common involvement of this pathway, possibly including scopoletin,
417 in the observed CK-mediated resistance phenomenon and a contribution to the CK-specific differences.

418 3.4.2 Defence-related genes

419 Since SA is known for its involvement in defence against *Pst* and in CK-mediated resistance
420 mechanisms, several SA marker genes were individually analysed. Expression of *ENHANCED*
421 *DISEASE SUSCEPTIBILITY 1 (EDS1)*, involved in signalling upstream of SA accumulation, *NON-*
422 *EXPRESSER OF PR-GENES 1 (NPR1)*, involved in downstream SA signalling, and the SA-responsive
423 defence marker genes *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED PROTEIN 1a (PR1a)* and *SYSTEMIC ACQUIRED*
424 *RESISTANCE 8.2a (SAR8.2a)* were differentially regulated by the tested CKs. While *EDS1* was not
425 responding to the CK treatments at 6h, it was strongly up-regulated at 24h by all CKs (Figure 5G).
426 Interestingly, 6-BAP and Kin resulted in a comparable lower upregulation than the other CKs, which
427 supports that Kin-mediated resistance in *N. tabacum* is not solely depending on SA (Großkinsky et al.,
428 2011), while SA may play a more important role in resistance mediated by other CKs and/or in other
429 pathosystems (Choi et al., 2010; Argueso et al., 2012; Großkinsky et al., 2013). *NPR1* showed a different
430 regulation pattern in response to the CKs. At 6h, its expression was not or slightly down-regulated,
431 except for 2-iP, which resulted in a relatively strong upregulation (Figure 5H). In contrast, 2-iP resulted
432 in the weakest upregulation of all tested CKs at 24h. The strongest, however moderate upregulation of
433 *NPR1* was observed after tZ treatment, followed by Kin, cZ, TDZ and 6-BAP, which had a comparable
434 impact as 2-iP. Expression of *PR1a* as a SA target was not regulated at 6h, and strongly up-regulated at
435 24h by all CKs but to different extents (Figure 5I). Upregulation of *PR1a* is in agreement with previous
436 observations in this and other pathosystems (Choi et al., 2010; Großkinsky et al., 2011; Argueso et al.,
437 2012), where a complex of ARR2 (Arabidopsis Response Regulator 2) and the transcription factor
438 TGA3 was showed to promote *PR1a* expression in Arabidopsis (Choi et al., 2010). The strongest
439 upregulation was found by tZ, 6-BAP and 2-iP, followed by Kin with an intermediate effect and cZ and
440 TDZ with a considerably lower upregulation. Interestingly, the regulation pattern of *PR1a* caused by the
441 CKs corresponds largely with *EDS1*. In contrast, the regulation of *SAR8.2* (Figure 5J) resembles roughly
442 the pattern found for *NPR1*, with the only difference that 6-BAP seemed to have a stronger relative
443 effect on *SAR8.2* than on *NPR1*. The differences between the zeatin isomers in regulating this SA-related
444 genes could contribute to their different efficiencies in restricting *Pst* infections. Interestingly, TDZ
445 which caused the strongest *Pst*-restrictive effect seems to result in a relatively low activation of the SA
446 pathway, which indicates the involvement of other factors contributing to its mechanism. Overall, SA
447 seems to be involved as a general mechanism in CK-mediated resistance, but varies depending on the
448 CK, plant species and pathogen. Since also other phytohormones can be responsive to CKs in the context
449 of resistance effects (Shigenaga et al., 2017), the expression of the JA receptor gene *CORONATINE*
450 *INSENSITIVE 1 (COI1)* and *ETHYLENE INSENSITIVE 2 (EIN2)*, involved in ethylene signalling, were
451 monitored (Figure 5K, L). *COI1* showed a generally very low expression compared to mock, but a trend
452 towards its upregulation by TDZ, cZ, tZ and 6-BAP at 6h was observed, and a downregulation by Kin
453 and 2-iP, while at 24h only 6-BAP remained above mock level (Figure 5K), indicating only a limited
454 and transient activation of JA signalling by some CKs. *EIN2* was down-regulated by all CKs except

455 Kin, which maintained an expression level comparable to the mock control (Figure 5L). Hence, the
456 observed CK-induced resistance and/or tolerance appear to be largely independent of these two
457 signalling pathways, with a minor impact on JA. This is supporting the observed induction of resistance
458 particularly towards infections with biotrophic pathogens such as *Pst*, as effective defence against this
459 type of pathogens should be associated with JA and ET pathways, involved in defence against
460 necrotrophs (Pieterse et al., 2012). In addition, the PR-genes *PR2b* encoding a beta-1,3-glucanase and
461 *PR3b* encoding a chitinase, which respond to different stresses and signalling compounds, were analysed
462 for their response to the tested CKs. Expression of *PR2b* was strongly down-regulated by all CKs at
463 both time-points, indicating no role of it in CK-mediated resistance (Figure 5M). In contrast, the
464 expression pattern of *PR3b* (Figure 5N) exhibited certain similarities to the pattern found for *NPR1* and
465 *SAR8.2a* and almost matches completely the pattern observed for *4CLI*. This hints at certain co-
466 regulations linking these genes and at their involvement in CK-specific activities related to disease
467 resistance.

468 *3.4.3 Genes related to carbohydrate metabolism and transport*

469 Based on the critical role of CK-induced extracellular invertase to induce sink metabolism in general
470 (Roitsch & Gonzalez, 2004) and specifically CK-mediated senescence (Lara et al., 2004) we have
471 assessed the regulation of extracellular invertase genes (Figure 6A-F), whereas the different isogenes
472 showed three distinct temporal dynamics. All tested CKs resulted at 24h in an induction of gene ID
473 3404g0040 (Figure 6A). The gene IDs 1933g0080 (Figure 6B), 24779g0010 (Figure 6C) and 3404g0020
474 (Figure 6D) showed a differential regulation. They notably all were repressed by 2-iP at 24h and induced
475 by most of the other CKs. This finding is in agreement with the characterization of other extracellular
476 invertase gene families with only specific isogenes induced by phytohormones or stress-related stimuli
477 (Godt & Roitsch, 1997; Roitsch & Ehneß, 2000; Roitsch & Gonzalez, 2004). Similar to the temporal
478 dynamics of the expression patterns of the GO term of amino acid transport (Figure S2C) also the
479 analyzed monosaccharide transporters showed a similar repression at 24h (Figure 6E, F).

480 *3.5 Targeted metabolomics identifies common and CK-type specific adjustments*

481 To gain further insight into how the transcriptional regulations translate into changes in the physiological
482 status of the plant tissue in response to control and CK treatments at the critical time-point of infection,
483 metabolites were extracted from respective leaf samples and analysed by targeted GC-MS- and LC-MS-
484 based metabolomics.

485 *3.5.1 Amino acid abundance is globally affected by CK treatments*

486 The presence of amino acids appeared to be generally much lower in CK-treated leaves, while adenine
487 showed only a minor effect on most amino acid pools (Table 2). Only the levels of arginine and
488 hydroxyproline were considerably lower after adenine treatment and at a comparable level as for CK
489 treatments. All CKs resulted in lower pools of all amino acid, with only a few exceptions. 2-iP treatment

490 resulted in considerable higher alanine levels, while 6-BAP and tZ had a neglectable effect, and cZ,
491 TDZ, and Kin treatments caused lower levels. 6-BAP is the only CK, which resulted in higher asparagine
492 levels, while much lower levels of 21 to 39 % were observed after treatments with any of the other CKs
493 compared to the mock control. Glycine levels were below detection limit after most CK treatments; only
494 after treatments with the zeatin isomers, glycine was detected, with the *trans*-isomer causing lower
495 levels, and the *cis*-isomer considerably higher levels of this amino acid compared to the control. The
496 generally low levels of amino acid pools appear to be a common CK effect and could be caused by
497 accelerated protein translation (Kulaeva, 1981; Szweykowska et al., 1981) as part of the growth/cell
498 cycle promoting activities of CKs and/or activation of specialised metabolic pathways in which specific
499 amino acids are used as building blocks/precursors (Hildebrandt et al., 2015; Yang et al., 2020;
500 Heinemann & Hildebrandt, 2021). Also, the enhanced expression of genes located in amino acid
501 catabolism in combination with regulations in amino acid biosynthesis genes observed for all CKs
502 (Figure S2) likely contribute to the lower amino acid levels. Although downregulation of genes involved
503 in amino acid biosynthesis has been observed, also considerable upregulation of genes was found, which
504 may hint at accelerated amino acid turnover rates that support the interpretation of enhanced protein
505 translation. However, correlation between amino acid pools and the impacts on *Pst* symptom
506 development and proliferation identified only a few potential links (Table S3). Alanine, arginine,
507 isoleucine, and phenylalanine levels at the time-point of *Pst* infection strongly positively correlated with
508 symptom development at the early scoring at 6 dpi, i.e., high levels of these amino acids correlate with
509 a strong symptom development. In contrast, methionine and the non-proteinogenic hydroxyproline
510 showed strong negative correlations with certain *Pst* infection proxies/scores. While methionine
511 accumulation exhibited a strong negative correlation with *Pst* proliferation at the latest analysis time-
512 point of 72 hpi, hydroxyproline is the only amino acid which strongly correlated with both *Pst* symptoms
513 (6 dpi) and proliferation (48 hpi). Hence, both amino acids may play a role in the underlying mechanisms
514 of CK-mediated resistance.

515 3.5.2 CK treatments affect the accumulation of acidic metabolites

516 Levels of most acidic metabolites analysed were higher after CK treatments compared to the controls
517 and usually changes were stronger than those caused by adenine (Table 2). Only L(-)-malic acid and
518 lactic acid levels were lower after all CK treatments. While L(-)-malic acid levels changed only slightly,
519 lactic acid levels were at only 47 to 59 % of the controls and also changes in response to adenine.
520 Succinic acid levels were slightly higher after all CK treatments except 2-iP, with tZ causing the
521 strongest increase of 46 % compared to the control. Oxalacetic acid, pyruvic acid and α -ketoglutaric
522 acid levels showed relatively homogenous increases of 77 to 114 %, 54 to 88 %, and 96 to 151 %,
523 respectively, after treatments with the different CKs. Citric acid and shikimic acid levels were 21 to 71
524 % and 17 to 31 %, respectively, higher after treatments with adenine-derived CKs. Strikingly, TDZ
525 treatment resulted in a 294 % increase in citric acid and 524 % increase in shikimic acid. As these two

526 metabolites strongly negatively correlate with *Pst* symptom development at both scoring time-points
527 (Table S3), these may directly contribute to mediating symptom-suppressive effects, which are most
528 prominent after TDZ treatment. As both are central to important plant metabolic pathways, the higher
529 levels may be indicative of a higher activity of these routes providing energy and metabolites to
530 stabilising the infected tissue and suppress *Pst* symptoms. Citric acid may in this context also directly
531 contribute to improved antioxidative defence (Sun & Hong, 2011; Hu et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2022).
532 Furthermore, the shikimic acid pathway is important for the formation of phenolic compounds including
533 the important defence phytohormone SA, antioxidants and antimicrobial phytoalexins, which can
534 strengthen resistance to pathogens (Santos-Sánchez et al., 2019; Shine et al., 2019). In contrast, L-(-)-
535 malic acid levels showed a strong positive correlation with *Pst* symptoms at both scoring time-points,
536 which indicates no role of this compound in preventing symptoms.

537 *3.5.3 Phenolic compounds are affected by CK treatments*

538 The analysed phenolic metabolites responded in a rather heterogenous pattern to the different CKs
539 (Table 2). Higher levels of 3-coumaric acid were generally found after CK treatments with the highest
540 levels in 6-BAP- and Kin-treated leaves. 3-hydroxybenzoic acid accumulated at higher levels after
541 adenine and CK treatments except 6-BAP, with the highest levels found in 2-iP- and Kin-treated leaves.
542 Kin caused also higher levels of ferulic acid, while all other CKs and adenine resulted in (partially much)
543 lower levels than in controls. None of these metabolites showed a strong correlation with *Pst* infection
544 scores (Table S3). Caffeic acid accumulated at slightly and protocatechuic acid at considerably lower
545 levels after all CK treatments, the latter also in adenine-treated leaves (Table 2). Accumulation of both
546 metabolites strongly positively correlated with *Pst* symptoms at 6 dpi (Table S3), indicating no specific
547 activities of these compounds in preventing symptoms. A comparable correlation was found for vanillic
548 acid, which was detected at lower levels in cZ-, Kin-, and TDZ-treated, and at higher levels in 2-iP- and
549 6-BAP-treated leaves (Table 2), the two CK treatments with strongest symptom development at 6 dpi.
550 Kaempferol levels changed only slightly in response to CKs (between +16 and -7 %; Table 2) but
551 correlated strongly positively with *Pst* symptoms at 12 dpi and *Pst* proliferation at 24 and 72 hpi (Table
552 S3) and may thus support infection establishment. Similarly, quercetin correlates with *Pst* proliferation
553 at 72 hpi, while it accumulated at clearly higher levels only in cZ-treated leaves, while levels were lower
554 in tZ-, 6-BAP-, 2-iP- and TDZ-treated leaves (Table 2). In comparison, chlorogenic acid was the only
555 phenolic compound analysed which negatively correlated with *Pst* symptoms at 6 and 12 dpi (Table S3).
556 Also, this metabolite accumulated at considerably higher levels in TDZ-treated leaves (Table 2), while
557 all other CKs had neglectable effects. Hence, chlorogenic acid could be one specific feature of the
558 extraordinarily efficient resistance against *Pst* mediated by TDZ compared to the other CKs, especially
559 considering its known antibacterial activity (Lou et al., 2011; Hammerschmidt, 2014).

560 *3.5.4 CK treatments affect carbohydrate, tocopherol and sterol levels*

561 Neither the levels of the saccharide groups quantified by LC-MS, nor the individual sugars quantified
562 by GC-MS correlated with *Pst* symptoms or proliferation (Table S3). While disaccharide and pentose
563 levels were rather higher after treatments with CKs and adenine, with the highest levels found in 2-iP-
564 treated leaves, hexose pools were found to be lower after all CK treatments except 2-iP, which caused
565 higher levels (Table 2). In accordance, fructose and glucose levels were found to be lower after all CK
566 treatments but 2-iP which resulted in higher accumulation of these sugars. This may hint at a weaker
567 promoting impact of 2-iP on sugar metabolism and energy turnover in comparison to the other CKs.
568 This may be causative for the relatively poor effect of 2-iP on stabilising plant tissue integrity and *Pst*
569 symptom suppression. Sucrose and myo-inositol levels were only slightly changed in response to CK
570 treatments, which tended towards lower levels except for 6-BAP, which resulted in slightly increased
571 levels.

572 α -tocopherol, campesterol and stigmasterol accumulated at slightly lower levels after CK treatments
573 with TDZ exhibiting the strongest overall effect (Table 2). All three compounds positively correlate
574 with the latest *Pst* proliferation monitored at 72 hpi, and campesterol and stigmasterol also correlate
575 with early *Pst* proliferation at 24 hpi and late symptom development at 12 dpi (Table S3). Hence, these
576 compounds may have an impact on the longer-term persistence of the infection process. Ergosterol,
577 fucosterol and β -sitosterol levels did not correlate with *Pst* symptoms or proliferation. Ergosterol
578 accumulated at a considerably lower level in TDZ-treated leaves, at slightly lower levels in 2-iP- and 6-
579 BAP-treated, and higher levels in cZ-, tZ-, and Kin-treated leaves (Table 2). Fucosterol levels tended to
580 be higher in CK-treated leaves, while β -sitosterol levels were lower except for 2-iP which caused a
581 considerably higher accumulation.

582 The phenylurea-derived TDZ shows often one of the strongest decreases in metabolites that positively
583 correlate and strongest increase in metabolites that negatively correlate with *Pst* infection scores
584 (symptoms and/or proliferation), which is in line with the overall strongest symptom- and proliferation-
585 suppressive effect observed (Figure 1). Hence, these metabolites may have specific functions that benefit
586 infection or resistance mechanisms, respectively. Where more general CK effects on the accumulation
587 of specific compounds were observed, 2-iP, 6-BAP and cZ were in several cases not following the trend.
588 These could be examples where certain functions shared by other CKs are differentially regulated by
589 these three CKs and not fully active to establish the complete resistance and/or tolerance against *Pst*.
590 These differences may partially explain the poor *Pst* symptom suppression through 2-iP, the relatively
591 poor early symptom suppression and restriction of *Pst* proliferation by 6-BAP and the poor restriction
592 of *Pst* proliferation by cZ. The limited effects of these CKs may be related to the dynamics of their
593 metabolism as well as their signalling efficiencies, which are inherently determined by their structures.
594 2-iP differs from the other CKs in relation to the temporal dynamic of the observed impact on transcript
595 and metabolite levels with a strong fast positive effect followed by a repression. This may be related to
596 the strong affinity of 2-iP to some groups of CK receptors shown for other plant species (Romanov,
597 2009; Stolz et al., 2011; Lomin et al., 2012). Thus, 2-iP may cause a very fast response evident at early

598 time points which is declined at later time points while other CKs are just starting to build up their
599 effects. Furthermore, since 2-iP is a good substrate for cytokinin oxidase/hydrogenases (Galuszka et al.,
600 2007; Kopečný et al., 2016), a high rate of degradation may contribute to the observation of no
601 considerable effects at the later timepoint of analysis, while the limited effect observed for 6-BAP may
602 be determined by a relatively fast and efficient conversion to N-glucosides (Gawer et al., 1977; Laloue
603 et al., 1981). In contrast, cZ has been shown to have a relatively low affinity to CK receptors. Although
604 there are plant-specific differences (Schäfer et al., 2015), it is generally lower compared to tZ (Romanov
605 et al., 2006; Stolz et al., 2011), which may be a major determinant of the relatively little effects of cZ
606 and the identified differences between the zeatin-isomers.

607 **4 Conclusions**

608 Our data provide comparative insights into the regulatory functions of diverse CK molecules, including
609 naturally occurring and artificial, as well as adenine- and phenylurea-derived CKs, in mediating
610 responses to pathogen infection and resistance. Different types of CKs were shown to differentially
611 impact *in-planta* pathogen proliferation and host plant symptom development as two partially
612 independent infection markers. The detailed analysis of their impact on these markers during *Pst*
613 infections identified their type-specific efficiencies in mediating resistance, which is determined by their
614 structure, and possibly related differences in their transport, signalling and metabolism. Subsequent
615 transcriptome and metabolome profiling revealed CK type-specific regulations, but also common
616 features shared by several CKs contributing to defence priming, resistance establishment and improving
617 the physiological status of the plant tissue. Transcriptome as well as metabolome profiling identified a
618 strong impact on amino acid abundance, regulation of central and specialised metabolites, as well as
619 important defence/resistance components. Hence, the results from both approaches support each other
620 well and allow for the estimation of general and CK-type specific functions.

621 The coordinated regulation of both primary carbohydrate metabolism and direct defence responses
622 resembles the impact of pathogen related stimuli (Ehness et al., 1997; Berger et al., 2007), with actually
623 the extracellular invertase, as one of the key enzymes of an apoplastic phloem unloading pathway and
624 sink metabolism (Roitsch & Gonzalez, 2004) as common metabolic target. Hence, these comparative
625 results help pinpoint underlying mechanisms in plant tolerance and resistance (and other processes)
626 mediated by CKs in general and at the level of specific CK molecules. Based on the transcriptional and
627 metabolic responses, the phenylurea CK TDZ and adenine CK 2-iP show some very distinct differences
628 compared to the other four tested CKs. Whereas TDZ is characterized by a strong activation of direct
629 defence reactions the 2-iP responses show a distinct temporal dynamic with a fast initial effect at 6h
630 which then strongly declines already at 24h. The presented data complements studies in which responses
631 to only one or two CKs were profiled in the same experimental setup (Schäfer et al., 2000; Brenner &
632 Schmülling, 2012; Raines et al., 2016; Bozsó & Barna, 2021). The knowledge gained increases our
633 understanding of CK activities in plant-pathogen interactions, their impacts on plant physiological and

634 defence mechanisms upon accumulation in response to other factors as well we their potential to develop
635 strategies for sustainable plant protection.

636 **Author contributions**

637 DKG conceived, designed, and performed experiments, generated, and processed material for
638 metabolomics and transcriptomics, analysed data, and drafted the manuscript with input from all other
639 authors. EMM analysed and visualised transcriptomics data. KE and FB performed experiments and
640 initial data analysis. MO and KV performed metabolomic measurements and initial data analysis. JT
641 supervised metabolomic analyses and contributed to experimental design. TR contributed to
642 experimental concept and design and data interpretation. All authors revised the manuscript and
643 approved the final version for submission.

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648 **Data availability statement**

649 The raw sequencing data that support the findings of this study are deposited in the NCBI Sequence
650 Read Archive (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra>) repository, BioProject accession number
651 PRJNA1101299. All other data are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Supporting Information

FIGURE S1. Molecular structures of used compounds.

FIGURE S2. Global gene expression patterns of the different CK treatments compared to mock for selected GO terms related to metabolic processes at 6 and 24h.

TABLE S1. Compounds quantified by LC-MS.

TABLE S2. Compounds quantified by GC-MS.

TABLE S3. Correlation coefficients for metabolite accumulation at 24h of different CK treatments and *Pst* symptom development and proliferation.

APPENDIX S1. Differentially expressed genes in tobacco leaves at 6h and 24h in response to different cytokinin treatments in comparison to the mock control.

Figures

FIGURE 1. Diverse cytokinins differentially impact *Pst* symptom development and proliferation.

(A) Symptom development 6 and 12 dpi with *Pst* in mock- and CK-treated leaves. Data represent means \pm S.E.M. of ≥ 81 individual infection sites (in minimum 27 individual leaves analyzed in ≥ 5 independent experiments). (B) *Pst* counts 0 to 72 hpi with *Pst* in mock- and CK-treated leaves. Data represent means \pm S.E.M. of ≥ 9 individual infection sites counted in triplicates (in minimum 9 individual leaves analyzed in ≥ 3 independent experiments). *, **, and *** indicate statistically significant differences based on two-sided, heteroscedastic Student's t-tests at $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$, and $p < 0.001$.

A

FIGURE 2. Global gene expression is differently regulated by different CKs. Differentially expressed genes at 6h (A, B) and 24h (C, D) of the indicated treatments. Bar graphs (A, C) comparatively visualise the absolute numbers of up- (grey) and down-regulated (black) genes for each treatment in comparison to the mock control. Venn diagrams (B, D) visualise the overlaps in gene regulations by different treatments normalised to adenine treatment as structural control.

FIGURE 3. Gene set enrichment analysis reveals CK-specific regulations. Gene set enrichments for the different CK treatments based on transcript profiling at 6h (A) and 24h (B).

A Response to stress (GO:0006950)

B Defence response (GO:0006952)

C Response to oxidative stress (GO:0006979)

FIGURE 4. Global gene expression patterns of the different CK treatments compared to mock for selected GO terms related to plant stress at 6 and 24h. Plots show log₂ fold change values of DEGs belonging to the GO terms response to stress (A), defence response (B), and response to oxidative stress (C) with regard to the different CK treatments compared to the mock control at 6 and 24h. Positive log₂ fold change values (representative for an upregulation of genes) are visualised in grey, negative values (representative for a downregulation of genes) in black.

FIGURE 5. Read counts of selected genes related to plant defence and resistance representing

common and CK-specific regulation. Plots show scaled read counts normalised to the mock control at 6 and 24h of indicated treatments for DEGs responsive to several or specific CKs. (A) *3-HYDROXY-3-METHYL-GLUTARYL-CoA REDUCTASE 1 (HMGR1)*, (B) *5-EPI-ARISTOLOCHENE SYNTHASE (EAS)*, (C) *PHENYLALANINE AMMONIA-LYASE 1 (PAL1)*, (D) *CINNAMIC ACID 4-HYDROXYLASE (C4H)*, (E) *4-COUMARATE:CoA LIGASE 1 (4CLI)*, (F) *TOBACCO GLUCOSYL-TRANSFERASE (TOGT)*, (G) *ENHANCED DISEASE SUSCEPTIBILITY 1 (EDS1)*, (H) *NON-EXRESSER OF PR-GENES 1 (NPR1)*, (I) *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED PROTEIN 1a (PR1a)*, (J) *SYSTEMIC ACQUIRED RESISTANCE 8.2a (SAR8.2a)*, (K) *CORONATINE INSENSITIVE 1 (COI1)*, (L) *ETHYLENE INSENSITIVE 2 (EIN2)*, (M) *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED PROTEIN 2b (PR2b)*, (N) *PATHOGENESIS-RELATED PROTEIN 3b (PR3b)*.

FIGURE 6. Read counts of selected genes related to carbohydrate metabolism and transport in response to CK treatments. Plots show scaled read counts for genes encoding extracellular invertases (A-D) and monosaccharide transporters (E & F) normalised to the mock control at 6 and 24h of indicated treatments for DEGs responsive to several or specific CKs.

Tables

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TABLE 1. Rankings of CK induced *Pst* symptom suppression and restriction of proliferation (based on Figure 1). 1 = strongest, 6 = weakest effect.

CK	Symptom suppression		Restriction of <i>Pst</i> proliferation		
	6 dpi	12 dpi	24 hpi	48 hpi	72 hpi
TDZ	1	1	1	2	1
cZ	2	4	6	3	2
Kin	3	5	4	1	3
tZ	4	2	3	4	4
6-BAP	5	3	5	6	5
2-iP	6	6	2	5	6

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TABLE 2. Metabolite accumulation at 24h of treatment with CKs and adenine in relation to NaOH as mock control. Ratios are based on mean values from 5 independent experiments with 3 technical replicates per sample consisting of 5 leaves. Colours indicate higher (blue) and lower (red) accumulation in relation to the mock control; colour shades indicate the extent of differences (per metabolite).

Metabolite	Mock	Adenine	2-iP	6-BAP	cZ	tZ	Kin	TDZ
<i>Compounds determined by LC-MS</i>								
<u>Amino acids</u>								
Alanine	1.00	0.93	1.47	1.04	0.82	0.95	0.66	0.80
Arginine	1.00	0.61	0.51	0.43	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.09
Asparagine	1.00	0.98	0.39	1.16	0.21	0.32	0.37	0.21
Aspartic acid	1.00	0.89	0.37	0.13	0.15	0.14	0.11	0.17
Cysteine	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Glutamic acid	1.00	0.88	0.68	0.45	0.47	0.41	0.39	0.45
Glutamine	1.00	0.76	0.05	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02
Glycine	1.00	1.14	<LOD	<LOD	1.90	0.79	<LOD	<LOD
Histidine	1.00	0.89	0.47	0.24	0.25	0.26	0.20	0.25
Hydroxyproline	1.00	0.52	0.49	0.50	0.51	0.44	0.58	0.58
Isoleucine	1.00	0.87	0.30	0.24	0.19	0.20	0.21	0.20
Leucine	1.00	0.88	0.32	0.23	0.18	0.18	0.19	0.19
Lysine	1.00	0.93	0.64	0.55	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD	<LOD
Methionine	1.00	0.77	0.34	0.33	0.24	0.31	0.31	0.34
Phenylalanine	1.00	0.86	0.79	0.84	0.67	0.73	0.73	0.65
Proline	1.00	0.81	0.61	0.80	0.39	0.40	0.44	0.53
Serine	1.00	0.90	0.33	0.22	0.22	0.18	0.19	0.17
Threonine	1.00	0.81	0.59	0.36	0.34	0.42	0.32	0.37
Tryptophan	1.00	1.05	0.80	0.61	0.67	0.69	0.68	0.60
Tyrosine	1.00	0.87	0.35	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.11	0.09
Valine	1.00	0.90	0.68	0.46	0.42	0.42	0.38	0.39
<u>Acids</u>								
Citric acid	1.00	0.96	1.21	1.43	1.50	1.51	1.71	3.94
L-(-)-Malic acid	1.00	0.98	0.92	0.87	0.87	0.88	0.86	0.82
Lactic acid	1.00	0.59	0.58	0.51	0.51	0.49	0.48	0.47
Oxalacetic acid	1.00	1.21	1.77	2.14	2.01	1.96	1.91	2.05
Pyruvic acid	1.00	1.30	1.54	1.88	1.84	1.68	1.56	1.61
Shikimic acid	1.00	1.19	1.24	1.31	1.21	1.17	1.28	6.24
Succinic acid	1.00	1.04	0.98	1.16	1.08	1.46	1.22	1.10
α -Ketoglutaric acid	1.00	1.14	1.96	2.51	2.28	2.50	2.49	2.30
<u>Phenolics</u>								
3-coumaric acid	1.00	0.84	1.22	1.63	1.16	1.24	1.52	1.40

3-hydroxybenzoic acid	1.00	1.20	1.79	0.98	1.35	1.08	1.56	1.15
Caffeic acid	1.00	1.04	0.99	0.98	0.92	0.96	0.85	0.82
Chlorogenic acid	1.00	1.04	0.98	1.02	1.03	0.96	1.04	1.43
Ferulic acid	1.00	0.66	0.85	0.70	0.52	0.58	1.19	0.94
Kaempferol	1.00	1.09	1.07	1.06	1.16	0.99	1.15	0.93
Protocatechuic acid	1.00	0.63	0.81	0.75	0.55	0.76	0.67	0.63
Quercetin	1.00	1.01	0.90	0.91	1.13	0.95	1.03	0.80
Vanillic acid	1.00	0.98	1.12	1.27	0.79	1.01	0.62	0.85
Saccharides								
Disaccharides	1.00	1.79	2.16	1.42	1.12	1.06	1.27	1.19
Hexoses	1.00	1.45	1.34	0.89	0.78	0.83	0.83	0.78
Pentoses	1.00	1.12	1.23	1.21	1.01	1.00	1.10	1.15
<i>Compounds determined by GC-MS</i>								
Sugars								
Fructose	1.00	0.97	1.26	0.76	0.60	0.66	0.56	0.67
Glucose	1.00	1.07	1.13	0.71	0.59	0.60	0.57	0.64
Sucrose	1.00	0.92	0.99	1.14	0.86	0.84	0.98	0.86
Myo-inositol	1.00	0.93	0.94	1.03	0.89	0.94	1.00	0.92
Tocopherol & sterols								
Campesterol	1.00	1.00	0.92	0.90	0.98	0.89	0.94	0.88
Ergosterol	1.00	0.72	0.93	0.92	1.21	1.39	1.38	0.68
Fucoesterol	1.00	1.03	1.04	1.14	1.06	1.01	1.14	1.12
Stigmasterol	1.00	1.01	0.97	0.97	0.98	0.91	0.97	0.93
α -tocopherol	1.00	0.97	0.91	0.81	0.92	0.82	0.82	0.80
β -sitosterol	1.00	1.04	1.63	0.91	0.99	0.85	0.95	0.90

